

PROCESSES OF INTRODUCING THE PERSON TO PERFORMING ART STYLES THROUGH MUSIC LISTENING.

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Annotation: this article describes in detail the reforms in the fields of education, culture, art and music in our country, the influence of music on the mind of a person, and the styles of performing arts.

Keywords: music, personality, mind, art, sport, musical art, thinking, work, analysis.

Annotatsiya: mazkur maqolada yurtimizdagi ta'lim, madaniyat, san'at va musiqa sohasidagi islohotlar, musiqaning shaxsning ongiga ta'siri, ijrochilik san'ati uslublari haqida batafsil yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: musiqa, shaxs, ong, san'at, sport, musiqa san'ati, tafakkur, asar, tahlil.

Аннотация: в данной статье подробно описаны реформы в сфере образования, культуры, искусства и музыки в нашей стране, влияние музыки на сознание человека, стили исполнительского искусства.

Ключевые слова: музыка, личность, разум, искусство, спорт, музыкальное искусство, мышление, труд, анализ.

It is clear to everyone that music has existed and developed since ancient times. Music has been used by people in various situations. At the same time, many of our scientists have mentioned in their works that music grows human thinking and develops it. Of course, it also depends on what kind of music we listen to. Nowadays, we are witnessing an increased attention to the fields of art and sports. Of course, the goal of this is to raise the young generation as a healthy, artistic and aesthetic taste, loyal to their people, and a perfect person. So, music is one of the leading types of education.[1]

In the field of music education, our president Sh. The first direction of the five important initiatives of Mirziyoev's "Strategy of Actions" 1 is music art and sports, which is aimed at making the young generation creative, spiritually mature, loving our motherland and protecting it. The foundation of knowledge begins with school and pre-school educational institutions. Our children get education in these places, grow spiritually and receive education. Therefore, we should not be indifferent to their educational processes, but constantly monitor them.[2] After all, the knowledge we are learning will determine our child's

future. Music also influences students' learning and thinking. In secondary schools, music lessons are held once a week. In these music lessons, children are engaged in several types of activities.

Music, first of all, educates artistic aesthetic taste and ethics in children. Activities such as music literacy, singing in a choir, listening to music, and creativity are carried out in an inextricably linked manner in music lessons. Among them, the activity of "listening to music" especially encourages the student to think. In this activity, the music teacher plays the necessary piece of music for the students to listen to based on the topic being taught, or plays it to the student through the technical means used in the lesson. For example, in middle classes, students listen to songs and statuses from the topic of Uzbek classical music and analyze it together. It is this process that greatly contributes to the development of the student's intelligence. This is the only way to achieve spiritual maturity and a rich cultural and spiritual heritage.[3]

That is, students learn to perceive music. Our songs and maqam poems are mainly taken from ghazals. And the ghazals describe love for the Great One, which inspires great contemplation and is deeply written in terms of meaning. Or we can see that the polyphony and fugues written by Johann Sebastian Bach on the subject of the work of foreign composers have a very positive psychological effect. We observe that his multi-voiced work served to focus attention and that each voice has its own content, and that voices combined to describe a whole complex work. In the activity of listening to music, students learn about the given piece of music, first of all, to perceive the mood of the music, the low pitch, rhythm, and timbre of the musical sounds. The content of the song is analyzed together with the teacher in the general conclusion. It is these processes that help in the development of the student's intelligence. Many studies have shown that music therapists have even treated patients by playing music.[4] When we listen to any kind of music, its character is visible in our facial expressions. For example, when we listen to music with a happy, fast rhythm, we immediately feel happy and uplifted.

On the contrary, if we listen to heavy and sad music, we will become more thoughtful. Psychotherapists have also mentioned that when listening to pleasant music, the internal organs of a person are synchronized. Therefore, properly selected music is also useful for the human body. In addition, sports lovers and sports enthusiasts enjoy listening to music almost every day. In this way, they feel that the processes of doing sports have been completed by getting

motivation for themselves. Psychologists have also mentioned that listening to music while doing sports increases work efficiency by 20%.

In Japan, one of the most developed countries, native language lessons are conducted in harmony with music in the primary and general education system. The reason for this is that it is easier for students to learn this subject through music. This is called the Suzuki system and it is very popular in Japan. Because music makes a great contribution to the understanding of other subjects. This method was created by the Japanese pedagogue and violinist Sinito Suzuki.

Since the research was successfully tested in practice, it was included in this educational system and named after the scientist who applied it to education. One of the most important aspects of music lessons is directed to the perception of listened music, teaching to analyze it with attention to its content. In order for these processes to be realized, all activities of music are created on the basis of such activities as musical literacy, singing and accompanying it with movements. Listening to music requires a music teacher to have skill and thorough knowledge of his profession.

Because it is important for the teacher to choose the right piece for “listening to music” according to the grade levels of the students. For example, when we are teaching elementary school students to listen to music, we cannot ask them to listen to complex polyphonic works or Uzbek classical music. [5] The musical perception of our young students is slow to analyze these works. Or, on the contrary, it is very easy for 7th graders to analyze simple children’s songs by listening to them.

Therefore, if we listen to music depending on the age and knowledge level of students, we will give them another impetus to develop their intellectual potential[6]. Listening to a piece of music over and over again makes it possible to retain it in the student’s memory and strengthen his knowledge about the piece. Students learn to articulate their impressions while analyzing it. At the beginning of the activity, the teacher should give some information about the piece to be listened to. For example, it explains the name of the work, when it was composed or performed, and what it is about. In this activity, students can evaluate the teacher's skills. If the work is performed by the teacher on some musical instrument, mainly on the piano, the work will be easier to understand and its impact on the minds of the students will increase. The effect of live performance is high.

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